

Effective cancer immunotherapy by natural mouse conventional type-1 dendritic cells bearing dead tumor antigen

Stefanie K. Wculek¹, Joaquín Amores-Iniesta¹, Ruth Conde-Garrosa¹,
Sofía C. Khouili¹, Ignacio Melero^{2,3,4} and David Sancho^{1,*}.

Additional file 1

- Supplemental Figures S1-S6
- Supplemental Figure legends

Figure S1. Isolation and phenotypic analysis of cDC1s from the spleen of FLT3L-expressing B16 tumor-bearing mice.

a & b CD8⁺ cDC1s were isolated from steady-state mice or mice harboring subcutaneous B16-FLT3L tumors as described in Methods. Yield was about 10⁵ cells/steady-state spleen and 1-5x10⁶ cells/B16-Flt3L-expanded spleen. **a** Representative flow cytometric analysis of cell purity of cDC1 preparation. Isolated cells were gated on alive (upper panel) and CD11c⁺ MHC-II⁺ cells (lower panel). **b** Representative flow cytometric analysis of cell surface marker expression on isolated CD11c⁺ MHC-II⁺ CD8⁺ cells. Antibody mix missing one antibody was used as negative staining control. One representative of ≥2 independent experiments is shown.

Figure S3. Adoptive cDC1 transfer-mediated endogenous CD8+ T cell responses are dependent on presentation on MHC-I of tumor Ag loaded onto cDC1s.

a Corresponding to Fig. 3b & c. Flow cytometric quantification of total CD8+ T cell number (left panel) and frequency of CD44+ H-2Kb-SIINFEKL+ within CD8+ T cells (right panel) in iLN 7 days after ID injection of control PBS or 5×10^5 poly I:C and B16-OVA TCL-loaded cDC1s. Combined data of 3 independent experiments with total $n=12$ (Control) and $n=13$ (cDC1s) mice are shown. $***P < 0.001$ by Student's *t* test. **b** Corresponding to Figure 3d-f. Flow cytometric quantification of total CD8+ T cell number (left panel) and frequency of CD44+ IFN γ -producing cells after re-stimulation with OVA₂₅₇₋₂₆₄ peptide within CD8+ T cells (right panel) in iLN 7 days after ID injection of control PBS, 5×10^5 poly I:C and B16-OVA TCL-loaded wildtype (WT) cDC1s or H-2K^{bm1}-harboring cDC1s. Combined data of 3 independent experiments with total $n=17$ (Control), $n=16$ (WT cDC1s) and $n=19$ (H-2K^{bm1} cDC1s) mice are shown. $***P < 0.001$ by one-way ANOVA and Tukey post hoc test.

Figure S4. Analysis of T cells in tumor-draining lymph node after administration of tumor Ag-loaded cDC1s.

Corresponding to Fig. 5. B16-OVA tumor-bearing mice were intradermally injected with PBS control or 10^6 poly I:C and B16-OVA TCL-loaded cDC1s and T cell response in the tumor-draining lymph node (tdLN) analyzed 3 days thereafter. Flow cytometric quantification of **a** total tdLN cell number, **b** CD8+ T cell number, **c** frequency of CD44+ PD-1+ in CD8+ T cells, frequency of IFN γ + in CD3+ CD8+ or CD3+ CD4- T cells after re-stimulation with **d** OVA₂₅₇₋₂₆₄ peptide or **e** B16-OVA TCL-loaded antigen-presenting cells (APCs), **f** CD8+ CD44+ H-2Kb-SIINFEKL+ T cell number and frequency with representative flow cytometric analysis (gated on CD8+ CD44+ cells), **g** CD4+ T cell number, **h** frequency of CD44+ PD-1+ in CD4+ T cells, frequency of IFN γ + in CD3+ CD4+ T cells after re-stimulation with **i** OVA₃₂₃₋₃₃₉ peptide-loaded APCs or **j** B16-OVA TCL-loaded APCs, **k** number and **l** frequency of CD4+ CD44+ T cells positive for a OVA-specific MHC-II tetramer mix as indicated in Methods. Combined data of 2 independent experiments with total n=12-17 (Control) and n=11-15 (cDC1s) mice are shown. *P<0.05, **P<0.01, ***P<0.001 by Student's *t* test.

Figure S5. Analysis of T cells in tumor after administration of tumor Ag-loaded cDC1s. Corresponding to Fig. 5. B16-OVA tumor-bearing mice were intradermally injected with PBS control or 10^6 poly I:C and B16-OVA TCL-loaded cDC1s and T cell response in the tumor analyzed 3 days thereafter. **a** Quantification of tumor weight, flow cytometric quantification of **b** total CD3+ CD8+ T cell frequency, **c** frequency of PD-1+ in CD3+ CD8+ T cells, **d** frequency of H-2Kb- SIINFEKL+ in CD3+ CD8+ T cells with representative flow cytometric analysis (gated on CD3+ CD8+ cells), **e** total CD3+ CD4+ T cell frequency, **f** frequency of PD-1+ in CD3+ CD4+ T cells and **g** frequency of CD3+ CD4+ T cells positive for a OVA-specific MHC-II tetramer mix as indicated in Methods. Combined data of 2 independent experiments with total n=12-17 (Control) and n=11-15 (cDC1s) mice are shown. *P<0.05, **P<0.01, ***P<0.001 by Student's *t* test.

Figure S6. UV irradiation-induced ICD of MC38 and B16/F10 cancer cells results in HMGB1 release and cDC1 activation.

a-d Corresponding to Fig. 6 and **e-g** corresponding to Fig. 7. **a & e** HMGB1 content measured by ELISA in supernatants of **a** MC38 and **e** B16/F10 cells treated with 25 μ M doxorubicin, 300mJ/cm² UV irradiation, 30 μ M Mitomycin C or 50 μ M Brefeldin A and cultured for 18hrs (n=3-4). ***P<0.001 by one-way ANOVA and Tukey post hoc test. **b, c, f & g** Quantification of **b & f** CD86 and **c & g** MHC-II expression on untreated cDC1s (Untreat.), cDC1s treated for 1h with **b & c** MC38 tumor cell lysate (TCL) or **f & g** B16/F10 TCL in presence or absence of 20 μ g/ml poly I:C. cDC1s were washed and cultured for 4 hours followed by flow cytometric analysis. The same untreated control groups (white and gray) are presented in **b & f** as well as in **c & g**, because data belong to the same experiments and are split for clarity. Combined data of 4 independent experiments. *P<0.05, **P<0.01, ***P<0.001 by paired Student's *t* test. MFI, mean fluorescence intensity. **d** Individual tumor growth of mice subcutaneously grafted with 10⁶ MC38 cancer cells followed by intradermal injection of PBS (Control and α PD-1-treated

groups) or 10^6 poly I:C and autologous MC38 TCL-loaded cDC1s (cDC1s- and cDC1s+ α PD-1-treated groups) at day 6 & 13 days as well as intraperitoneal injection of PBS (Control and cDC1s-treated groups) or 100 μ g anti-PD-1 antibody (α PD-1- and cDC1s+ α PD-1-treated groups) at day 7, 10, 14 & 17. Number of animals that rejected the tumor out of total mice/group are indicated in the upper left corner in every graph. Combined data of 2 independent experiments with total n=18 (Control, α PD-1 and cDC1s+ α PD-1-treated groups) and n=19 (cDC1s-treated group) mice are shown.